

1 **Population genetics of *Ixodes scapularis* Say, 1821 in the United States using**
2 **microsatellite loci: more than a North-South phenomenon.**
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36 **ABSTRACT**

37 The genetic structure of *Ixodes scapularis* has been investigated using a wide array
38 of tools. Microsatellite markers have successfully been used to analyze the genetic structure
39 of many tick species, but only of localized populations of *I. scapularis*. Here, nine
40 microsatellite loci and two mitochondrial gene sequences were used to analyze populations
41 of this tick species at 28 sites throughout its distribution range. There was no congruence
42 between the topologies of the mitochondrial and microsatellite phylogenetic analyses,
43 confirming that mitochondrial maternal lineages do not accurately capture the full structure of
44 the population. The hierarchical level "Site" contributed significantly to population subdivision
45 with a corresponding fixation index $F=0.0461$ (p -value <0.001). The East-West component of
46 subdivision was more significant than the frequently emphasized North-South component.
47 Within subsamples (defined as ticks belonging to one site and one cohort) loci were not
48 significantly affected by linkage-disequilibrium (p -value >0.075). A basic $F_{IS}=-0.1981$ in
49 95%CI=[-0.3546, -0.0416], suggested that, across the tick's range in general, *I. scapularis*
50 populations are small and locally pangamic. Overall, isolation by distance was significant
51 across all subsamples. Nevertheless, this signal varied considerably between the different
52 zones. The signal was weak for eastern data, consistent with bigger and/or more connected
53 subpopulations in this region, although a non-equilibrium situation caused by frequent
54 perturbations could also be an explanation. In contrast, in more western regions, particularly
55 in Texas, isolation by distance was much more pronounced. Overall, effective population
56 sizes were small, indicating that survival rate of eggs and immature ticks might be lower than
57 expected. This was further corroborated by the fact that most sites displayed significant
58 bottleneck signatures.

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60 **Keywords:** population genetics, microsatellite, *Ixodes scapularis*

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62 INTRODUCTION

63 *Ixodes scapularis* Say, 1821 (Acari:Ixodidae) is the main vector of *Borrelia*
64 *burgdorferi*, the Lyme disease agent, in the eastern United States. While the tick is
65 distributed and is vector competent throughout most of the eastern part of the country, the
66 prevalence of the pathogen in host-seeking ticks varies, with high-risk areas found in the
67 Northeast and Upper Midwest and low-risk areas spanning the southern states from Florida
68 to Texas (Eisen et al., 2016; CDC, 2019). Several hypotheses have been developed to
69 explain the geographic difference in pathogen prevalence, including difference in tick
70 densities, in questing behavior, and in local composition of vertebrate host communities
71 (Ostfeld and Keesing, 2000; Diuk-Wasser et al., 2010; Stromdahl and Hickling, 2012; Arsnøe
72 et al., 2019) . A recent ecological study, with extensive geographic tick and host sample
73 representation, has shown that a combination of selective host preference for lizards
74 (Ginsberg et al., 2022), different host-seeking behaviors, and lower tick densities in the South
75 can explain the observed geographic pattern of Lyme disease in the U.S. (Ginsberg et al.,
76 2021).

77 The observed behavioral differences could be ascribed not only to local adaptation to
78 different environmental features, but to population structure identifiable only through
79 population genetics analyses. Several molecular tools have been used to explore the genetic
80 diversity of *I. scapularis*. The earliest studies aimed at verifying whether or not the northern
81 and southern ticks were different species. *Ixodes dammini* Spielman, Clifford, Piesman &
82 Corwin, the northern tick, was relegated to junior synonym of *I. scapularis* based on
83 reciprocal crosses, karyotype, and isozyme analyses (Oliver et al., 1993). Phylogenetic
84 analyses of mitochondrial gene sequences have repeatedly identified a genetically
85 homogeneous “American clade” found throughout the tick geographic range and a
86 genetically diverse “southern clade”, found exclusively in the southern states. In the South,
87 American and southern clade haplotypes coexist, while only American clade haplotypes are
88 found in the North (Norris et al., 1996; Qiu et al., 2002). Genotype distribution has been
89 explained in part through an analysis of the climatological events that shaped North America

90 after the last glacial maximum (Xu et al., 2020). Analyses of some nuclear gene sequences
91 (Xu et al., 2020) and SNPs (Van Zee et al., 2015) have also revealed the occurrence of
92 divergence between northern and southern populations. With few exceptions (Norris et al.,
93 1996; Sakamoto et al., 2014), most of the sampling in the mentioned publications was limited
94 to ticks collected along the Atlantic coast and the upper Midwest, with ticks occurring along
95 the Gulf Coast going unstudied.

96 Microsatellite markers have been used successfully to study fine-scale genetic
97 diversity in many tick species and genera (McCoy et al., 2001; De Meeûs et al., 2002; De
98 Meeûs et al., 2004; McCoy et al., 2005; Chevillon et al., 2007; Kempf et al., 2009a; Kempf et
99 al., 2009b; De Meeûs et al., 2010; Kempf et al., 2011; Paulauskas et al., 2018). For some
100 time, however, these tools were not considered to be useful for analyzing populations of *I.*
101 *scapularis*, possibly because earlier evaluations of microsatellite abundance in the tick
102 suggested they were infrequently found in its genome (Fagerberg et al., 2001). This was later
103 contradicted when the full genome of *I. scapularis* was sequenced (Hill and Wikel, 2005;
104 Meyer et al., 2010). Microsatellite markers have since been used for the analysis of the
105 expansion pattern of *I. scapularis* at the Canadian border (Leo et al., 2017; Talbot et al.,
106 2020). We have described elsewhere the development and scoring treatment of different
107 microsatellite markers we developed for *I. scapularis* (De Meeûs et al., 2021).

108 Here, we analyzed the geographic genetic structure of populations of *I. scapularis*
109 throughout its distribution range in the U.S. (including the Gulf Coast states) by using nine
110 previously described loci and the dataset “cured” of short allele dominance and stuttering
111 previously described (De Meeûs et al., 2021). For each genotyped tick, we also amplified two
112 mitochondrial gene sequences (12SrDNA and D-loop) to verify whether or not mitochondrial
113 and microsatellite markers provided congruent information.

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115 **MATERIAL AND METHODS**

116 **Sampling**

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118 Collection data are presented in Table 1, and in Figure 1, both previously used in (De
119 Meeûs et al., 2021).

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Figure 1 (from De Meeûs et al, 2021). Sampling sites for *Ixodes scapularis* from the U.S.

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State codes as in Table 1

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138 Table 1: State, site, GPS coordinates (decimal degrees), membership of clades resolved
 139 using 12SrDNA and D-loop mitochondrial sequences, date of sampling, corresponding
 140 cohort membership and size of *Ixodes scapularis* adult subsamples (N) from the U.S.
 141

State	Site	Latitude	Longitude	Clade	Date	Cohort	N
Alabama	AL1	33.24	-86.13	AMI	2011 Jan	C7	21
	AL1	33.24	-86.13	SOI	2011 Jan	C7	6
	AL1	33.24	-86.13	AMII	2011 Jan	C7	18
	AL1	33.24	-86.13	SOII	2011 Jan	C7	6
	AL2	32.95	-87.14	AMI	2012 Dec	C9	3
	AL2	32.95	-87.14	AMII	2012 Dec	C9	2
Connecticut	CT1	41.35	-72.76	AMI	2001 Nov	C1	3
	CT1	41.35	-72.76	AMI	2003 Jun	C2	21
Florida	FL1	30.65	-84.21	SOII	2012 Dec	C9	4
	FL2	30.06	-81.37	AMI	2011 Jan	C7	2
	FL2	30.06	-81.37	AMII	2011 Jan	C7	3
	FL2	30.06	-81.37	SOI	2011 Jan	C7	1
	FL2	30.06	-81.37	SOII	2011 Jan	C7	4
Georgia	GA1	32.45	-81.78	AMI	2009 Dec	C5	11
	GA1	32.45	-81.78	SOI	2009 Dec	C5	5
	GA1	32.45	-81.78	SOII	2009 Dec	C5	17
	GA1	32.45	-81.78	SOIII	2009 Dec	C5	1
Iowa	IA1	42.67	-91.59	AMI	2007 May	C3	3
Louisiana	LA1	30.94	-91.46	AMI	2012 Dec	C9	3
	LA1	30.94	-91.46	AMII	2012 Dec	C9	2
	LA1	30.94	-91.46	SOIII	2012 Dec	C9	1
	LA1	30.94	-91.46	SOIV	2012 Dec	C9	2
Massachusetts	MA1	41.71	-69.92	AMI	2010 May	C5	6
Maryland	MD1	39.29	-76.88	AMI	2010 Oct	C7	11
North-Carolina	NC1	33.91	-78.39	AMI	2009 Jan	C4	22
	NC1	33.91	-78.39	SOI	2009 Jan	C4	4
	NC1	33.91	-78.39	SOIII	2009 Jan	C4	2
New-York	NY1	40.76	-72.83	AMI	2009 Oct	C5	10
Pennsylvania	PA1	40.67	-75.96	AMI	2010 Oct	C7	5
	PA2	41.06	-79.48	AMI	2014 May	C10	33
South-Carolina	SC1	33.33	-81.66	AMI	2011 Apr	C7	8
	SC1	33.33	-81.66	AMII	2011 Apr	C7	1
	SC1	33.33	-81.66	SOI	2011 Apr	C7	3
	SC1	33.33	-81.66	SOII	2011 Apr	C7	1
	SC1	33.33	-81.66	SOIII	2011 Apr	C7	1
	SC2	33.23	-81.73	AMI	2010 Dec	C7	4
	SC2	33.23	-81.73	AMII	2010 Dec	C7	8
	SC2	33.23	-81.73	SOI	2010 Dec	C7	4
	SC2	33.23	-81.73	SOII	2010 Dec	C7	10
	SC3	33.15	-81.61	SOII	2010 Dec	C7	2
	SC5	34.29	-79.87	AMI	2012 Dec	C9	3
SC5	34.29	-79.87	SOII	2012 Dec	C9	2	
Tennessee	TN1	35.37	-86.07	AMI	2010 Dec	C7	23
Texas	TX1	31.80	-96.23	AMI	2012 Dec	C9	5
	TX1	31.80	-96.23	SOI	2012 Dec	C9	2
	TX1	31.80	-96.23	SOIV	2012 Dec	C9	3
	TX2	30.24	-100.72	AMI	2012 Dec	C9	1
	TX2	30.24	-100.72	SOIV	2012 Dec	C9	5
	TX3	31.91	-95.9	AMI	2012 Dec	C9	3
	TX3	31.91	-95.9	SOI	2012 Dec	C9	2
	TX3	31.91	-95.9	SOIV	2012 Dec	C9	6
	TX4	31.59	-95.61	AMI	2012 Dec	C9	2
TX4	31.59	-95.61	SOI	2012 Dec	C9	2	
Virginia	VA1	38.29	-78.29	AMI	2010 Oct	C7	7
	VA2	37.32	-80.73	AMI	2012 Dec	C9	4
Wisconsin	WI1	43.95	-90.70	AMI	2011 Oct	C8	8
	WI1	43.95	-90.70	AMI	2012 Oct	C9	4
	WI2	44.04	-90.65	AMI	2011 Oct	C8	8
	WI2	44.04	-90.65	AMI	2012 Oct	C9	12
	WI3	44.02	-90.64	AMI	2011 Oct	C8	8
WI3	44.02	-90.64	AMI	2012 Oct	C9	3	

144

145 **Genotyping**

146 All data had already been “cured” of short allele dominance and stuttering in a prior
147 publication (De Meeûs et al., 2021). Microsatellite raw data are available in Supplementary
148 Table S1, also from De Meeûs et al. (2021).

149

150 **Cohort membership**

151 Ticks from several years were available. We considered that a cohort consisted of
152 adult ticks sampled in the fall of year t and the spring of year $t+1$ (Daniels et al., 1989;
153 Daniels et al., 1996). Following this, cohort 1 (C1) corresponded to ticks sampled in
154 November 2001 (in CT); C2 to ticks sampled during April-June 2003 (in CT); C3 during May
155 2007 (in IA), C4 during January 2009 (in NC); C5 during October-December 2009 and spring
156 2010 (in MA, GA, and NY); C6 during June-August 2010 (in SC); C7 during October-
157 December 2010 and January-April 2011 (in AL, FL, MD, PA, SC, TN, and VA); C8 during
158 October 2011 (in WI); C9 during fall 2012 (in AL, FL, LA, SC, TX, VA, and WI); and C10 (in
159 PA) (Table 1).

160

161 **Clade membership**

162 Samples were subdivided in clades based on phylogenetic analyses of a dataset (866
163 base pairs) obtained by concatenating partial 12SrDNA and D-loop mitochondrial gene
164 sequences of each tick (486 ticks). Primers and PCR conditions for the amplification of these
165 genes have been previously described (Beati and Keirans, 2001; Beati et al., 2013). The
166 sequences were aligned and concatenated with Mesquite 3.61 (Maddison and Maddison,
167 2021). Duplicate sequences were eliminated and the resulting dataset (257 sequences) was
168 analyzed phylogenetically with MrBayes 3.2.5 (Huelsenbeck and Ronquist, 2001; Ronquist et
169 al., 2012). Two analyses, with four chains each, were run simultaneously for BA analyses
170 (1,000,000 generations). Trees were sampled every 100 iterations with a 25% burning
171 fraction. The 50% majority-rule consensus tree of the remaining trees was inferred, and

172 posterior probabilities were recorded for each branch. Homologous sequences of *Ixodes*
173 *affinis* Neumann, 1899, a closely-related taxon, were used as outgroup. For more details and
174 GenBank accession numbers, see (Chan, 2012).

175

176 **Microsatellite-based phylogeny and mitochondrial clades.**

177 To verify whether or not mitochondrial clade assignments bore any similarity with the tree
178 topology inferred by neighbor-joining analysis of microsatellite-based distances, the entire
179 sample (adult, nymphal and larval stages) was first divided into subsets belonging to a
180 specific mitochondrial clade and geographic site (e.g. SOII-SC1 for ticks clustering in clade
181 SOII and collected at site SC1; see results section). The microsatellite-based genetic
182 distance was the chord distance of Cavalli-Sforza and Edwards (Cavalli-Sforza and Edwards,
183 1967) (D_{CSE}). Because null alleles were known to occur (De Meeûs et al., 2021), we
184 corrected distance values for their presence by applying the INA method implemented in
185 FreeNA, after missing data were recoded as homozygous for allele 999 (putative null
186 homozygotes) (Chapuis and Estoup, 2007). The D_{CSE} matrix was used to build a neighbor-
187 joining tree as recommended in (Takezaki and Nei, 1996).

188

189 **Hierarchical levels of population structure**

190 For this and all subsequent analyses, only adult stages were considered to avoid
191 Wahlund effects due to lumping of immature stages from the same clutches (De Meeûs et
192 al., 2021). The different possible levels at which hierarchical subdivisions occur was explored
193 with the HierFstat package (Goudet, 2005). The first level, NorthSouth (the most inclusive),
194 was defined by northern sites (north of NC) versus southern sites. The second level (Area)
195 defined four areas, two in the North, North-East and North-West, separated by the Great
196 Lakes, and two in the South, South-East and South-West, separated by the Mississippi River
197 (Table S1 and Figure 1). The last level, Site, corresponded to the sites illustrated in Fig. 1
198 and listed in Table 1.

199 Hierarchical analyses can only take into account nested factors, e.g. Site, nested in
200 an Area, nested in a Region, nested in the Total Sample. Therefore, temporal factors cannot
201 be taken into account in this kind of analyses because they would represent crossed factors
202 (e.g. December 2012 concerns different Sites from different Regions) (De Meeûs and
203 Goudet, 2007). Consequently, our datasets had to be reduced to contemporaneous
204 subsamples (same cohort) of adult ticks: cohorts 5, 7, 8 and 9 only. For these four datasets,
205 HierFstat computed estimates of Yang's hierarchical F -Statistics (Yang, 1998). We were
206 interested in the effect of Site relative to Area (F_{SA}), effect of Area relative to NorthSouth
207 (F_{AN}) and, finally, effect of NorthSouth relative to the Total Sample (F_{NT}). To test the
208 significant effect of each of these levels, HierFstat uses a randomization G -based procedure.
209 For F_{SA} , individuals were randomized across sites within the same area; for F_{AN} , sites were
210 randomized across the different areas within the same NorthSouth zone; and finally, for F_{NT} ,
211 areas were randomized across NorthSouth zones. The number of randomizations was set to
212 1000. Detailed descriptions of the procedure can be found in De Meeûs and Goudet's tutorial
213 paper (De Meeûs and Goudet, 2007). We then averaged these F 's across cohorts 5, 7, 8 and
214 9 and combined associated p -values with the generalized binomial procedure (Teriokhin et
215 al., 2007) using MultiTest v 1.2 (De Meeûs et al., 2009). The script is available in Appendix 1.

216

217 **Dataset formatting**

218 Create v 1.38 (Coombs et al., 2008) was used to format the dataset for Fstat 2.9.4
219 (Goudet, 2003) (updated from (Goudet, 1995)).

220

221 **Quality testing of loci**

222 Quality testing of loci, stuttering and short allele dominance corrections were
223 undertaken as described in a previous article, where mitochondrial clade assignments were
224 taken into consideration to define subsamples (De Meeûs et al., 2021). In the present paper,
225 because of the results obtained in section "*Microsatellite-based phylogeny and mitochondrial*
226 *clades*", clades could be safely ignored. Therefore, unless specified otherwise, the

227 subpopulation unit in this article is the Site (individual location where ticks were collected:
228 Tables 1 and S1).

229 Statistical independence between loci was appraised with the multi-subsample G -
230 based test of F_{stat} with 10,000 associations at random of genotypes at the two loci for each
231 pair of loci in each subsample. The G 's are then summed over all subsamples. The p -value
232 of the test is the proportion of time a randomized G was as big as or bigger than the G
233 computed on the real data set. This procedure was shown to be the most powerful to
234 combine tests of linkage disequilibrium (LD) between locus pairs over subsamples (De
235 Meeûs et al., 2009). There are as many tests as there are possible locus pairs (here 36) and
236 these tests are not independent. We thus adjusted the p -values with the Benjamini and
237 Yekutieli (BY) false discovery rate method (Benjamini and Yekutieli, 2001) computed with R v
238 4.0.5 (R-Core-Team, 2020). The consequences of a Wahlund effect on LD were tested with
239 the correlation between the number of times a locus is found in a significant pair and its total
240 genetic diversity measured by Nei's H_T (Nei and Chesser, 1983). For this, we used a two-
241 sided Spearman's rank correlation test as described in a previous article (Manangwa et al.,
242 2019), with the R-commander (rcmdr) R-package (Fox, 2005; Fox, 2007).

243 Population genetics structure was evaluated by computing Wright's F -statistics, which
244 estimate relative levels of inbreeding at different levels of biological organization (Wright,
245 1965). F_{IS} measures inbreeding of individuals relative to inbreeding of subsamples; F_{ST}
246 measures inbreeding of subsamples relative to total inbreeding; and F_{IT} measures inbreeding
247 of individuals relative to total inbreeding. In other words, F_{IS} quantifies the deviation of
248 observed genotypic proportions from the values expected under random mating; F_{ST}
249 evaluates the effect of subdivision; while F_{IT} results from both these influences. These
250 statistics were estimated with Weir and Cockerham unbiased estimators (Weir and
251 Cockerham, 1984) computed with F_{stat} 2.9.4. In order to correct for the presence of null
252 alleles, we used the ENA algorithm implemented in FreeNA to compute F_{ST_FreeNA} .

253 Genetic diversity was assessed with Nei's unbiased estimators H_S and H_T (Nei and
254 Chesser, 1983), within subsamples and over all, respectively and computed with F_{stat} .

255 Confidence intervals at 95% (95%CI) were computed with jackknife over subsamples or
256 5000 bootstraps over loci as described elsewhere (De Meeûs et al., 2007) with Fstat.

257

258 **Isolation by distance**

259 Isolation by distance was studied with Rousset's model in two dimensions (Rousset,
260 1997): $F_R = a + b \times \ln(D_{Geo})$, where $F_R = F_{ST_FreeNA} / (1 - F_{ST_FreeNA})$ is Rousset's index of genetic
261 differentiation between subsample pairs, a and b are the intercept and the slope of the
262 regression, and $\ln(D_{Geo})$ is the natural logarithm of the geographic distance between
263 subsample pairs. It was shown that if this regression is significant, the slope can be used to
264 compute the size of the neighborhood $Nb = 1/b$ and the number of immigrants, from
265 surrounding subpopulations, entering in each subpopulation at each generation
266 $N_e m = 1 / (2 \times \pi \times b)$ (Rousset, 1997). The product $D_e \times \overline{\sigma^2} = 1 / (4 \times \pi \times b)$, where D_e is the
267 effective population density and $\overline{\sigma^2}$ is the average of squared axial distance between adults
268 and their parents, can also be computed. If D_e can be estimated separately, a rough proxy of
269 dispersal distance per generation can be calculated as $\delta = 2 \sqrt{1 / (4 \times \pi \times b \times D_e)}$ (Séré et
270 al., 2017). Geographic distances were assessed using the GPS coordinates (in decimal
271 degrees) of each subsample with the package geosphere (Hijmans et al., 2019) for R. The
272 corresponding script is available in Appendix 2.

273 Paired F_{ST} and 95% CI, between each pair of contemporaneous subsamples (same
274 cohort), were estimated with the ENA algorithm implemented in FreeNA (Chapuis and
275 Estoup, 2007) with 5,000 bootstraps over loci, after recoding missing genotypes as null
276 homozygotes for allele 999. We then studied Rousset's regression with these estimates. The
277 regression was considered significant if the lower limit of the 95% CI of the slope was greater
278 than 0. If not significant, because the regression/bootstrap procedure is not always powerful
279 enough, we also undertook a Mantel test based on the chord distance from Cavalli-Sforza
280 and Edwards (Cavalli-Sforza and Edwards, 1967). We corrected this genetic distance for
281 presence of null alleles (D_{CSE_FreeNA}) by the INA algorithm with FreeNA (Chapuis and Estoup,

282 2007), as recommended (Séré et al., 2017). This test was undertaken with the "Mantelize it"
283 procedure of Fstat 2.9.4, known to work on non-squared matrix, as is the case here (because
284 non-contemporaneous subsample pairs were excluded). We set the number of permutations
285 at 10,000. The software generates two-sided p -values. One-sided p -values were then
286 computed as half the p -value in case of positive correlation, or as $1-p$ -value/2 otherwise.

287

288 **Effective population sizes, densities, and dispersal distances**

289 Effective population sizes (N_e) were computed with different programs and methods.
290 We used the heterozygote excess method of Balloux (Balloux, 2004) where $N_e = -1/(2F_{IS}) -$
291 $F_{IS}/(1+F_{IS})$ and F_{IS} is Weir and Cockerham estimator of Wright's F_{IS} computed by Fstat. We
292 also used NeEstimator v 2.1 (Do et al., 2014) that implements, both, the LD based method
293 (Waples, 2006), with the correction for missing data (Peel et al., 2013), and the coancestry
294 method (Nomura, 2008). We also estimated effective population sizes with the intra- and
295 inter- loci identity method (Vitalis and Couvet, 2001b) with Estim 1.2 (Vitalis and Couvet,
296 2001a). For the LD based method, we only kept estimates for alleles with a frequency of at
297 least 0.05, as recommended in the user manual of NeEstimator v 2.1.

298 Subsequently, we averaged these values to obtain N_{e_a} across methods and sites.
299 The averages were weighted by the number of usable values. We also computed averages
300 of minimum and maximum values across methods to obtain a range of possible N_e values.
301 We compared different N_e between areas with the Welch F test that does not assume
302 homogeneity of variances with the package rcmdr.

303 Real densities were estimated from 63 sites in nine states where systematic sampling
304 was undertaken on a given surface, with two supplementary states: Rhode Island (RI) and
305 New-Jersey (NJ). Questing ticks were collected for an on-going multi-site study comparing the
306 ecology of the blacklegged tick and enzootic cycle of *Borrelia burgdorferi*. Sampling was
307 conducted every 2-3 weeks from May to September (depending on the weather) and then
308 monthly from October to April for southern sites (due to the lack of snow). Some sites (WI, MA,
309 TN, SC) were sampled from 2010-2012; some were sampled from 2011-2012 (NJ, NC, AL,

310 FL). All sites comprised three 1-ha grids, with the exception of RI, which comprised of 2 grids.
311 Additionally, sampling on some grids were precluded in some years due to habitat destruction
312 and/or extreme weather events (AL, NC). Questing ticks were collected by a combination of
313 dragging and flagging a 1 m² flannel cloth as previously described (Rulison et al., 2013; Ogden
314 et al., 2018; Ginsberg et al., 2021). The cloth was inspected every 15 m; all ticks were removed
315 and placed into vials of 95% ethanol. The area dragged per grid per sample was 720 m². Thus,
316 the total area sampled per sampling period for 2 and 3 grids was 1440 m² and 2160 m²
317 respectively. The density of questing adult ticks collected by dragging/flagging per site was
318 estimated as the total number of adult ticks collected among all grids divided by the total
319 amount of area sampled among all grids throughout the period of analysis for a cohort. This
320 provided an index of the densities of detectable ticks per km² (D_c). For comparison of means
321 between states or between areas we undertook Welch F tests. For multiple comparisons
322 between sample pairs we used the Tukey contrast implemented by R-Commander.

323 Effective population densities were computed by dividing the total effective population
324 sizes by the surface of the entire zone defined by sites used to genotype adult ticks. We
325 evaluated the surface occupied by a tick subpopulation (S_s) by standardizing according to
326 the surface occupied by sites from Wisconsin (WIA1, WIA2 and WIA3), because these were
327 shown to behave as a single randomly mating population (see Results). We then used
328 percentage of counties where *I. scapularis* was considered to be established in 2015 (P) in
329 Eisen et al.'s Table 1 (Eisen et al., 2016). We took the surface of each state (S_{St_i}) (i standing
330 for the state) and multiplied it by $P/100$ to approximate the surface occupied by this tick in
331 each state ($S_{Sto_i} = S_{St_i} \times P/100$). The total surface in the USA occupied by *I. scapularis*
332 (S_{O_Tot}) was then computed by the sum of all S_{Sto_i} 's. We then obtained the putative total
333 number of tick subpopulations in the USA as $n_T = S_{O_Tot}/S_s$. The effective population size over
334 all the USA was then computed as $N_{eT} = n_T \times N_{e_a}$. The total surface of the zone where adult
335 ticks were genotyped (S_T), corresponded to a tetrahedron defined by the four most external
336 sites (WI1, MA1, TX2 and FL2). The effective population density was then obtained as $D_{eT} =$
337 N_{eT}/S_T . Surfaces were measured with the command `areaPolygon` of the `geosphere` package

338 (Appendix 1). For the total surface, we also used the sum of surfaces of all concerned states
339 which was $S_{\text{sum}}=4,974,562 \text{ km}^2$.

340 Dispersal distances per generation were then calculated as

341
$$\delta = 2 \times \sqrt{1/(4 \times \pi \times b \times D_{eT})}$$

342

343 **Sex specific genetic structure**

344 To test for the existence of a sex specific genetic structure we used the biased
345 dispersal menu of Fstat with 10,000 permutations, separately in cohorts 5, 7, 8 and 9. We
346 used the corrected average assignment index A/c , the variance of this index vA/c and the F_{ST}
347 (Goudet et al., 2002; Prugnolle and De Meeûs, 2002). We averaged these quantities across
348 the four cohorts and combined the corresponding p -values with the generalized binomial test
349 with MultiTest.

350 We first tested for biased dispersal test with F_{ST} , to check which gender dispersed
351 less, and then undertook all tests unilaterally.

352

353 **Bottleneck signature**

354 We also investigated bottleneck signatures by using Bottleneck (Cornuet and Luikart,
355 1996). We only used subsamples of at least five individuals. We used the Wilcoxon signed
356 rank test, for the IAM model, the TPM model with default parameters, and the SMM model
357 (Cornuet and Luikart, 1996). We accepted the hypothesis of a bottleneck signature when all
358 three tests gave a significant p -value. Since we were interested in detecting a bottleneck in
359 each individual site, we used the Benjamini and Hochberg (BH) false discovery rate
360 correction (Benjamini and Hochberg, 1995), with R (command `p.adjust`). We compared the p -
361 values between areas with Welch's F test and the paired comparisons with Tukey's contrasts
362 with `rcmdr`.

363

364 **RESULTS**

365 **Mitochondrial clades phylogenetic analyses**

366 The phylogenetic reconstruction identified the expected basal “southern” clades and
367 the monophyletic “American” clade (Fig. 2A). The southern haplotypes clustered in four
368 genetically diverse and paraphyletic groups. The “American” clade was characterized by the
369 occurrence of a large unresolved polytomy (American I) (corresponding to ticks collected in
370 every area of the tick geographical distribution), and its sister lineage exclusively found in the
371 southern states (American II). Clade representatives were not equally distributed
372 geographically (Fig. 2B). For instance, lineage South II was found in the Southeast, while
373 South IV was only found at more southwestern longitudes. In the northern part of the
374 geographic range of *I. scapularis*, only clade Am I was observed, while all clades (including
375 AmI) were recorded from southern latitudes.

376 Therefore, instead of subdividing our sample into two main clades (“American” and
377 “Southern”), we assigned each tick to a specific cluster within these clades (Am I = polytomy,
378 Am II = southern clade within the “American” lineage, South I, South II, South III, and South
379 IV) (Fig. 2A-B).

380

381 Fig. 2: (2A) Phylogenetic reconstruction of relationships among mitochondrial clades of
 382 *Ixodes scapularis* from USA, inferred by Bayesian analysis; posterior probabilities are
 383 indicated over branches; the scale corresponds to number of substitutions/site. (2B)
 384 Geographic distribution of the mitochondrial haplotypes; colors in pie-charts
 385 correspond to colors of clades in the phylogenetic tree.

386

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389 **Distribution of clades within the microsatellite-based neighbor-joining tree**

390 The results of this analysis are presented in Fig. 3. Although there is no real clade
 391 support in this reconstruction, there is an indication of geographic grouping. Mitochondrial
 392 clade membership distributes randomly among southern lineages clearly indicating that the
 393 information provided by analyzing the two types of markers is not congruent. Therefore, all

394 following analyses were based on microsatellite data alone, while clade membership was
395 ignored.

396

397 Figure 3: Neighbor-joining tree base on a D_{CSE} matrix for 9 microsatellite data of subsamples
398 of *Ixodes scapularis* from the U.S. Each mitochondrial clade is represented by a
399 different color and OTUs include clade code and geographic origin by site.

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419 Hierarchical levels of population structure

420 The results of these analyses are detailed in Table 2. For cohorts 5 and 8, only Site
421 level could be tested (with Fstat). For cohort 7, only Site and NorthSouth could be tested

422 (with HierFstat). Over the four analyses (cohorts 5, 7, 8 and 9), Site contributed significantly
 423 to population subdivision with a $F_{SA}=0.0461$ (p -value <0.001). In cohort 9, the East-West
 424 separation could be tested and appeared significant, while the North-South contribution
 425 appeared insignificant in cohorts 7 and 9 together. We thus kept Site for subsequent
 426 analyses and ignored other levels, except when specified otherwise. Corresponding scripts
 427 with detailed results are available in Appendix 1.

428

429 Table 2 Results of the hierarchical F analyses on microsatellite data undertaken for cohorts
 430 5, 7 and 9 of *Ixodes scapularis* in eastern USA. Results are given for sites in areas
 431 (F_{SA}), areas in NorthSouth zones (F_{AN}), and NorthSouth in the total sample (F_{NT}) (see
 432 the Material and Methods section for more details).

Cohort	F_{SA}		F_{AN}		F_{NT}	
	Value	p-value	Value	p-value	Value	p-value
5	0.075	0.017	NA	NA	NA	NA
7	0.092	0.001	NA	NA	0.023	0.687
8	-0.008	0.887	NA	NA	NA	NA
9	0.0395	0.023	0.0560	0.037	0.06275	0.186
All	0.0461	<0.001	0.0560	0.037	0.0429	>0.5

433

434

435 Population genetics structure within subsamples

436 Subsamples corresponded to combinations of site and cohort membership. Eight
 437 locus pairs among 36 (22%) presented a significant LD (p -values <0.05). None of these p -
 438 values stayed significant after BY correction (p -values >0.075). The correlation between the
 439 number of times a locus was found in a significant pair and the total genetic diversity, though
 440 positive, was not significant ($\rho=0.4807$, p -value $=0.1902$). According to the criterion of

441 Manangwa et al (2019), the absence of correlation does not support the LD being caused by
442 a Wahlund effect within sites (see also F_{IS} analyses below).

443 Across the nine loci, there was an agreement between observed genotypic
444 proportions and the expected ones under panmixia: $F_{IS}=-0.011$ in 95%CI=[-0.11, 0.108] (p -
445 value=0.2068). Variation across loci was mainly explained by null alleles as demonstrated in
446 a previous paper (De Meeûs et al., 2021). If loci with important proportions of null alleles
447 were removed (loci IR27, IS11 and IS19, Figure 5 in (De Meeûs et al., 2021)), there was a
448 significant heterozygote excess $F_{IS}=-0.085$ in 95%CI=[-0.181, -0.019] (bilateral p -
449 value=0.0002) as expected in small dioecious subpopulations. The regression of F_{IS} against
450 missing data (putative null homozygotes) with 95%CI of jackknives, provided positive slopes
451 and negative intercepts. If we assume that intercepts provide a raw proxy of F_{IS} without null
452 alleles, these intercepts provided a basic $F_{IS}=-0.1981$ in 95%CI=[-0.3546, -0.0416],
453 confirming small and pangamic populations for *I. scapularis*. Such results are incompatible
454 with a Wahlund effect.

455

456 **Isolation by distance**

457 Isolation by distance was tested over all subsamples, within northern and within
458 southern subsamples, within areas as defined in S1, but also within eastern and western
459 zones. There was a significant isolation by distance across all subsamples, with a slope
460 $b=0.0224$ in 95%CI=[0.0385, 0.012]. This trend was also found in northern subsamples,
461 $b=0.0149$ in 95%CI=[0.0268, 0.007], and in southern subsamples, $b=0.014$ in
462 95%CI=[0.0306, 0.0072]. There was no signature of isolation by distance across
463 southeastern sites. This was confirmed by a Mantel test on D_{CSE_FreeNA} , even when
464 subsamples with less than 10 individuals were excluded. On the contrary, southwestern sites
465 (Texas) displayed a strong isolation by distance signature: $b=0.0655$ in 95%CI=[0.0169,
466 0.149]. Within eastern zones taken as a whole, the signal was not significant: $b=-0.001$ in
467 95%CI=[-0.00251, 0.003]. With the Mantel test, we obtained a p -value=0.1321. Nevertheless,
468 when we excluded subsamples with less than 10 individuals, a weak but significant isolation

469 by distance was observed: $b=0.0016$ in $95\%CI=[-0.0015, 0.01]$, Mantel test p -value= 0.0194 .

470 On the contrary, a strong signal was observed in the West: $b=0.0402$ in $95\%CI=[0.0175,$

471 $0.0766]$. These slopes translated into a neighborhood size that strongly depended on the

472 geographical area (Figure 4). In particular, neighborhoods appeared much bigger in the East.

473

474 Figure 4: Inferences of neighborhood sizes (number of individuals), from isolation by distance

475 slopes, in different geographic areas of *Ixodes scapularis* in the U.S. estimated from

476 microsatellite markers. Confidence intervals (black dashes) came from 5000

477 bootstraps over loci (infinity not represented)

478

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480

481 We tried to study the importance of subdivision by sites within areas where isolation

482 by distance was not significant (Southeast, NorthWest, NorthEast) or weak (East). In these

483 areas, we compared F_{IS} within sites with F_{IS} within cohorts (sites of the same cohort pooled).

484 The difference was tested with a one-sided Wilcoxon signed rank test for data paired by loci.

485 A significant difference would mean a higher F_{IS} in cohorts (Wahlund effect). All differences

486 were significant except in North-West (i.e. in Wisconsin cohorts 8 and 9) (Table 3).

487

488 Table 3: Detection of Wahlund effect when pooling *Ixodes scapularis* ticks of the same cohort
 489 from different sites within specific geographic areas from the U.S. The values of F_{IS}
 490 before (F_{IS_site}) and after pooling (F_{IS_cohort}) and the one sided p -value ($F_{IS_site} < F_{IS_cohort}$)
 491 are indicated for each type of areas.

Areas	F_{IS_site}	F_{IS_cohort}	p -value
Southeast	0.032	0.077	0.0020
Southwest	-0.166	-0.115	0.0195
East	0.013	0.062	0.0020
Northeast	-0.025	-0.006	0.0020
Northwest	-0.086	-0.091	0.9629

492
 493 Consequently, the northwestern sites (the three sites from Wisconsin) can be
 494 considered as belonging to a single subpopulation. For other sites, even if very weak, sites
 495 play a significant role, and the absence or weakness of isolation by distance may be due to a
 496 very slow genetic drift (very big effective population sizes and/or long range dispersal
 497 distances), and/or to a situation of non-equilibrium (recent perturbations).

498 When considering northern and southern sites separately, to study the East-West
 499 migration pattern, we found rather similar values for the slope, with $b \approx 0.01$ in 95%CI $\approx [0.007,$
 500 $0.03]$ in both zones.

501
 502 **Effective population sizes, densities, and dispersal distances**

503 The average effective population size was $N_{e_a} = 56$ with an average range
 504 $\text{minimax} = [5, 436]$. These were not significantly different among the four areas (p -
 505 $\text{value} = 0.4514$). However, densities of captured ticks did vary (Figure 5). Western sites
 506 appeared to have higher tick densities than eastern sites, while no difference could be
 507 observed between North and South.

508

509 Figure 5: Observed tick densities (ticks/km²) in different states (codes as in the material and
 510 methods section) and areas with 95% confidence intervals (black dashes):
 511 NE=Northeast, SE=Southeast, and NW=Northwest. Results of the Welch *F*-tests are
 512 indicated by letters. Members of the same letter were not significantly different from
 513 each other's.

516 Effective population densities were poorly correlated with observed densities
 517 ($\rho=0.1429$, p -value=0.3913), due to "outlier" values in North and South Carolina. If these two
 518 states are removed, the correlation was improved ($\rho=0.7$, p -value=0.1167). With S_T , the
 519 effective population densities were $D_{eT_T}=2.2$ in $\text{minimax}=[0.2, 16.9]$ individuals per km².
 520 Using S_{sum} , provided smaller values $D_{eT_{\text{sum}}}=1.2$, in $\text{minimax}=[0.1, 9]$. Such quantities yielded
 521 rather small dispersal distances (Figure 6). Depending on the method used (using S_T or
 522 S_{sum}), averages was between 2.5 in 95%CI=[1.9, 3.4] and 3.4 in 95%CI=[2.6, 4.7]
 523 km/generation, respectively. The range of minimum and maximum values was between
 524 $\text{minimax}=[0.9, 8.4]$ and $\text{minimax}=[1.3, 11.5]$ km/generation.
 525

526 Figure 6: Average dispersal distance (δ) for *I. scapularis*, in km, per generation in the U.S.
 527 Estimates were computed using the total surface defined by sampling sites (S_T), or
 528 with the sum of the surfaces of all states where the tick was established in 2015
 529 (Eisen et al., 2016) (S_{sum}), and using the weighted average effective population size
 530 across subsamples and methods (N_e), the average minimum (N_{e_min}) or maximum
 531 (N_{e_max}) (see text for more details).

532

533

534 Detailed results are available in the Supplementary File S2.

535

536 Sex-specific genetic structure

537 Results are presented in Table 4. Average F_{ST} appeared bigger in males than in
 538 females. Unilateral tests were thus computed for a female-biased dispersal (females
 539 disperse more). Test results converged to a marginally significant signal (in italics in Table 3).

540

541 Table 4: Results for the sex-biased dispersal tests across *Ixodes scapularis* subpopulations
 542 in different cohorts. Values of the different statistics used and associated p -values are
 543 indicated. Values corresponding to the less dispersive gender are in bold. Tests were

544 one-sided for a female-biased dispersal (females disperse more). The p -values
 545 obtained over all cohorts (generalized binomial procedure) are in italics.

Cohort	Gender	F_{ST}	p -value	Ai_c	p -value	vAi_c	p -value
C5	F	0.0283	0.3331	-0.1831	0.0954	14.5300	0.4403
	M	0.0369		0.3520		3.4577	
C7	F	0.0884	0.1487	-0.2246	0.0260	9.5822	0.1190
	M	0.1208		0.2916		5.6193	
C8	F	-0.0121	0.0201	-0.2246	0.1893	9.5822	0.2676
	M	0.0227		0.2916		5.6193	
C9	F	0.0928	0.3675	-0.2246	0.8567	9.5822	0.1299
	M	0.1321		0.2916		5.6193	
All	F	0.0494	<i>0.1079</i>	-0.2142	<i>0.0480</i>	10.8191	<i>0.0846</i>
	M	0.0781		0.3067		5.0789	

546

547

548 **Bottleneck signature**

549 Most sites displayed a highly significant bottleneck signature. Welch's anova was
 550 inconclusive, but some sites displayed higher p -values. In particular, Wisconsin's sites, and
 551 North-Eastern sites generally displayed the smallest p -values. Nevertheless, the global
 552 p value was not significant (p -value=0.1683). Eastern sites presented smaller p -values as
 553 compared to Western ones, but the difference was marginally not significant (p -
 554 value=0.1115). There was absolutely no difference between North and South. More details
 555 can be found in the Supplementary File S2.

556

557 **DISCUSSION**

558 The mitochondrial phylogenetic analysis confirmed most of what had been published
 559 in earlier studies (Norris et al., 1996; Qiu et al., 2002; Sakamoto et al., 2014) . However, our
 560 data show a pattern that had yet to be clearly outlined: samples that were usually assigned to

561 the “American” clade cluster in two supported sister lineages (Am I and Am II), with Am I
562 covering the whole distribution of *I. scapularis* and Am II exclusively found in the South
563 (corresponding to haplotypes IX in (Norris et al., 1996). Also, the basal very diverse southern
564 lineages are paraphyletic and do not cluster in a monophyletic group. This might be due to
565 different choices in outgroup taxa or the fact that our sample extended further along the Gulf
566 of Mexico, in Tennessee, Alabama, Louisiana, and Texas than previous studies. The
567 heterogeneous distribution of haplotypes in the South is indicative of prolonged past isolation
568 of populations of *I. scapularis* along their East-West distribution. Comparative
569 phylogeographical analyses of organisms that diversified in unglaciated eastern North
570 America in the Pleistocene revealed similar phylogenetic topologies for several terrestrial
571 organisms (Soltis et al., 2006) and, interestingly so, also for the main host of *I. scapularis*,
572 *Odocoileus virginianus* (Zimmermann, 1780) (Ellsworth et al., 1994; Soltis et al., 2006).
573 Divergence in the South appears to have been maintained through the effect of riverine and
574 terrestrial discontinuities (Soltis et al., 2006). As for the American clade, it also finds its origin
575 in the South and only Am I corresponds to the population of *I. scapularis* that has colonized
576 the North following a recent bottleneck event (Xu et al., 2020). The analysis of mitochondrial
577 genes can inform on past phylogeographic events that have driven distribution of maternal
578 lineages. It is, nevertheless, obvious that mitochondrial clades do not translate into present
579 nuclear tick lineages, as was shown in the neighbor-joining tree inferred from microsatellite-
580 based genetic distances, where southern clade representatives were often found more
581 closely related to American clade representatives than to other southern lineages.

582 Despite evidence of weak population subdivision in eastern populations, it appeared
583 that our sampling sites represented significant levels of subdivision. In Wisconsin we were
584 able to estimate that a subpopulation of *I. scapularis* occupies a surface of $S_S \approx 13.063 \text{ km}^2$. It
585 is true that sites in Wisconsin were geographically very close. This estimate could not be
586 confirmed in other areas where sites were too distant from each other. It would be useful to
587 confirm this estimate by sampling more and closer sites in each of the other areas. It is,
588 however, worthy of note that, while some of the Texas sites were also geographically close,

589 they still exhibited significant subdivision. Furthermore, although it is difficult to compare data
590 obtained with totally different methods, significant genetic structure was also found among
591 populations in a relatively small area in the state of NY (O'Keeffe et al., 2022).

592 The relatively higher significance of the East-West component, when compared to
593 North-South, is interesting because it reveals an aspect of the genetic structure of *I.*
594 *scapularis* that had yet to be fully explored, possibly for lack of samples from Texas and
595 Louisiana from earlier studies. The focus on differences between northern and southern
596 populations is certainly justified epidemiologically. Nevertheless, our data are a strong
597 indication that this tick species has diversified not only latitudinally, but also longitudinally.

598 We found a significant isolation by distance across all the geographic range of *I.*
599 *scapularis* in the U.S., with rather small effective population densities of approx. one tick per
600 km², which yielded rather small dispersal distances of at most 16 km per tick generation.
601 Given that a generation is ~2 years based on northeastern studies (Piesman and Spielman,
602 1979; Daniels et al., 1996) (and potentially 3 in the middle west), all dispersal distances must
603 be halved for an annual dispersal distance. Our values are compatible with dispersal speed
604 reported from the state of NY along the expansion edge of the tick distribution (Khatchikian et
605 al., 2015). It is, however, much smaller than the front range expansion of 35-55 km/year
606 proposed by Leighton et al. (2012) in their study of the progression of *I. scapularis* in
607 Canada. However, it is obvious that these estimates should not be directly compared
608 because our estimate covers the whole eastern U.S. with a wide range of underlying
609 differences in ecologies and environmental features (altitude, local climate, host fauna, and
610 anthropogenic landscape modifications) that can hamper or facilitate tick dispersal and/or
611 establishment. Indeed, this pattern appeared quite variable, and probably under the influence
612 of local constraints, and/or local disturbances in recent history, i.e. no more than a few tens
613 of generations ago (Leblois et al., 2004) (less than 90 years). In contrast, the fast rate of
614 northward range expansion is likely the consequence of a specific combination of events:
615 annual dispersion of ticks carried northward (and north of current range limits of reproducing

616 tick populations), which, with recent climate warming, have become founder populations
617 effecting a “pulled” range expansion (Ogden et al. 2010; 2013)

618 A strong signal of isolation by distance among southwestern populations (i.e. Texas)
619 suggests patchy distribution of populations of around five detectable adults per km² and
620 rather shorter dispersal distances of at most 4 km per generation. Overall, this would mean
621 that the environment is relatively viscous to these ticks, thus limiting not only the tick
622 dispersal/establishment but also that of the pathogens they transmit. Pathogens can,
623 however, be carried by avian vertebrate hosts (Ginsberg et al., 2005, Loss et al., 2016) over
624 long distances resulting in uncoordinated phylogeographic patterns of pathogens and ticks
625 (Humphrey et al., 2010). In contrast, a marginally not significant signal was observed among
626 eastern sites, with much longer dispersal distances with maximum values over 22 km per
627 generation. This could possibly indicate that, unlike for ticks in the Southwest, dispersal
628 along the Atlantic Coast relies relatively more often on avian hosts. The eastern coast of the
629 U.S. is a known bird migratory flyway. In general, it appears that dispersal through proximity
630 expansion (on small mammals, and deer) is more important than long distance events
631 (Khatchikian et al., 2015; O’Keeffe et al., 2022). Ticks may be carried over long distances by
632 birds, but only if the new environment is suitable, might they survive and establish new
633 populations (Cohen et al., 2015).

634 Local disturbances were also suggested by the unexpected highly significant
635 bottleneck signature that affected almost all sites, and the particularly low estimated effective
636 population densities (which do not correspond to observed densities). This would suggest
637 that there is a very weak individual probability of any particular tick transmitting genes to the
638 next generation. Survival of larval and nymphal ticks depend on many natural environmental
639 conditions (Ginsberg and Zhioua, 1996; Brunner et al., 2012; Ginsberg et al., 2014; Ginsberg
640 et al., 2017), but landscape changes caused by urbanization, habitat fragmentation (Allan et
641 al., 2003; Ogrzewalska et al., 2011; Khatchikian et al., 2015), fires, and extreme weather
642 associated with climate change can add to the sources of bottlenecks.

643 We found a significant isolation by distance in northern sites. This contrasts with
644 recent findings in Canadian ticks (Leo et al., 2017; Talbot et al., 2020). However,
645 in this zone of range spread the situation is dynamic with founder populations likely
646 establishing, dying out and re-establishing due to ticks imported by migratory birds (Clow et
647 al. 2017), so here it may be too early to detect significant isolation by distance. However, in
648 the present paper and unlike these other papers, we controlled for date of sampling and for
649 amplification problems, which are important to avoid biased estimates of gene flow (Séré et
650 al., 2017; Manangwa et al., 2019; De Meeûs et al., 2021; De Meeûs and Noûs, 2022).
651 Moreover, our subsample sizes were bigger: 11 adults on average per site, seven sites with
652 more than 20 individuals, against no more than 14 individuals (and most of the time less) per
653 sites in Leo et al. (2017) and Talbot et al. (2020) papers. These differences in sample sizes
654 and data analyses may explain these discrepancies

655 Finally, all tested parameters indicated female biased dispersal, but with a weakly
656 significant signal for the corrected assignment index. This finding contradicts observations for
657 the related *Ixodes ricinus* L. in Europe (De Meeûs et al., 2002) and, therefore, will require
658 additional more specific investigation.

659 While this is a first evaluation of the structure of *I. scapularis* at the continental scale,
660 there is no doubt that finer scale population genetic studies can likely further clarify some of
661 the puzzling findings presented in this work.

662

663

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938

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945 **Disclaimer:** Any use of trade, firm, or product names is for descriptive purposes only and
946 does not imply endorsement by the U.S. Government

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APPENDICES

950

951 **Appendix 1: Scripts for the HierFstat analyses**

952 Data in the appropriate format are available in the following text files:

953 C5-FSTAT.dat (for Fstat)

954 C7-HierFstat.txt (Test NorthSout and Site)

955 C8-FSTAT.dat (for Fstat)

956 C9-HierFstat.txt

957

958 *For cohort 5 (Fstat analysis for sites)*

959 Over all loci

960 Capf Theta Smallf

961 0.08 0.075 0.006

962 Bootstrapping over Loci.

963

964 95% Confidence Interval.

965

966 CapF theta Smallf

967 -0.068 -0.014 -0.093

968 0.258 0.225 0.082

969

970 IR27 Prop rand. larger than observed in [0.088

971 IS1 Prop rand. larger than observed in [0.0169

972 IS3 Prop rand. larger than observed in [0.0169

973 IS11 Prop rand. larger than observed in [0.6046

```

974 IS15 Prop rand. larger than observed in [ 0.5711
975 IS16 Prop rand. larger than observed in [ 0.5597
976 IS17 Prop rand. larger than observed in [ 0.9999
977 IS18 Prop rand. larger than observed in [ 0.7544
978 IS19 Prop rand. larger than observed in [ 0.1979
979 All Loci Prop rand. larger than observed in [ 0.0169
980
981 Script for cohort 7
982 > data<-read.table("C7-HierFstat.txt", header=TRUE)
983 > attach(data)
984 > loci<-data.frame(IR27,IS1,IS3,IS11,IS15,IS16,IS17,IS18,IS19)
985 > levels<-data.frame(NorthSouth, Site)
986 > varcomp.glob(levels,loci)
987 $loc
988      [,1] [,2] [,3] [,4]
989 IR27 0.098450723 0.02772948 -0.0136692356 0.7760000
990 IS1 0.002429347 0.02258996 -0.0189864449 0.9185185
991 IS3 -0.026501670 0.11254747 -0.0570610649 0.6250000
992 IS11 0.052462595 0.10408534 0.2925397980 0.4682540
993 IS15 0.006701887 0.04193205 0.0007930756 0.8968254
994 IS16 0.042156926 0.03610922 -0.0468079446 0.4146341
995 IS17 -0.005267064 0.01147403 0.0602568222 0.3560606
996 IS18 0.023718645 0.11800406 -0.0958673758 0.8512397
997 IS19 -0.043286959 0.12167703 0.0274181605 0.4360902
998
999 $overall
1000 NorthSouth Site Ind Error
1001 0.1508644 0.5961486 0.1486158 5.7426225

```

```

1002
1003 $F
1004      NorthSouth      Site      Ind
1005 Total      0.02272653 0.11253160 0.13491939
1006 NorthSouth 0.00000000 0.09189349 0.11480191
1007 Site      0.00000000 0.00000000 0.02522658
1008
1009 test.within(loci,test=Site,within=NorthSouth,nperm=1000)
1010 $p.val
1011 [1] 0.001
1012
1013 > test.between(loci,rand.unit=Site,test=NorthSouth,nperm=1000)
1014 $p.val
1015 [1] 0.687
1016
1017 For cohort 8 (FstatAnalysis for sites)
1018 Over all loci
1019   Capf  Theta  Smallf
1020 -0.068 -0.008 -0.059
1021
1022      Bootstrapping over Loci.
1023
1024      95% Confidence Interval.
1025
1026      CapF  theta  Smallf
1027 -0.299 -0.031 -0.274
1028  0.165  0.021  0.169
1029

```

```

1030      Number of complete multilocus genotypes in the different samples:
1031          4
1032
1033 IR27  Prop rand. larger than observed in [ 0.6791
1034 IS1   Prop rand. larger than observed in [ 0.2361
1035 IS3   Prop rand. larger than observed in [ 0.5867
1036 IS11  Prop rand. larger than observed in [ 0.4566
1037 IS15  Prop rand. larger than observed in [ 0.8219
1038 IS16  Prop rand. larger than observed in [ 0.9999
1039 IS17  Prop rand. larger than observed in [ 0.87
1040 IS18  Prop rand. larger than observed in [ 0.9218
1041 IS19  Prop rand. larger than observed in [ 0.9262
1042 All Loci      Prop rand. larger than observed in [ 0.8867
1043
1044 Script for cohort 9, with a single North entity
1045 > data<-read.table("C9-HierFstat.txt", header=TRUE)
1046 > attach(data)
1047 > loci<-data.frame(IR27,IS1,IS3,IS11,IS15,IS16,IS17,IS18,IS19)
1048 > levels<-data.frame(NorthSouth, Area, Site)
1049 > varcomp.glob(levels,loci)
1050 $loc
1051      [,1]  [,2]  [,3]  [,4]  [,5]
1052 IR27 0.012903661 0.063600214 0.006764710 0.04532107 0.7638889
1053 IS1  0.012882597 0.009830606 0.015780374 -0.03958174 0.9420290
1054 IS3  -0.036517784 0.075914906 0.031362974 -0.12533294 0.6164384
1055 IS11 0.300570630 -0.014438950 0.036006568 0.13288054 0.4852941
1056 IS15 0.009525827 0.019428616 0.016545836 -0.05768876 0.9264706
1057 IS16 0.045693297 0.016051648 0.020240326 -0.14503067 0.7397260

```

1058 IS17 -0.001016818 0.024579312 0.007022706 -0.05872777 0.5205479
1059 IS18 0.075450105 0.080431734 0.059558953 -0.25304859 0.9452055
1060 IS19 0.004294978 0.129225322 0.066171425 -0.17785521 0.5217391

1061

1062 \$overall

1063 NorthSouth Area Site Ind Error

1064 0.4237865 0.4046234 0.2594539 -0.6790641 6.4613395

1065

1066 \$F

1067 NorthSouth Area Site Ind

1068 Total 0.06168528 0.1205812 0.15834669 0.05950384

1069 NorthSouth 0.00000000 0.0627678 0.10301597 -0.00232485

1070 Area 0.00000000 0.0000000 0.04294364 -0.06945200

1071 Site 0.00000000 0.0000000 0.00000000 -0.11743890

1072

1073 > test.within(loci,test=Site,within=Area,nperm=1000)

1074 \$p.val

1075 [1] 0.007

1076

1077 > test.between.within(loci,within=NorthSouth,rand.unit=Site,test=Area,nperm=1000)

1078 \$p.val

1079 [1] 0.104

1080

1081 > test.between(loci,rand.unit=Area,test=NorthSouth,nperm=1000)

1082 \$p.val

1083 [1] 0.339

1084

1085

```

1086  Script for cohort 9: Area=NorthWest, NorthEast, SouthWest and SouthEast
1087  > data<-read.table("C9Bis-HierFstat.txt", header=TRUE)
1088  > attach(data)
1089  > loci<-data.frame(IR27,IS1,IS3,IS11,IS15,IS16,IS17,IS18,IS19)
1090  > levels<-data.frame(NorthSouth, Area, Site)
1091  > varcomp.glob(levels,loci)
1092  $loc
1093      [,1] [,2] [,3] [,4] [,5]
1094  IR27 0.031055454 4.890136e-02 0.007096913 0.04532107 0.7638889
1095  IS1 0.008569778 2.087387e-02 0.009261375 -0.03958174 0.9420290
1096  IS3 -0.023444284 7.595052e-02 0.022609158 -0.12533294 0.6164384
1097  IS11 0.290837492 7.889002e-05 0.030324138 0.13288054 0.4852941
1098  IS15 0.017815730 8.783603e-03 0.020012388 -0.05768876 0.9264706
1099  IS16 0.034655288 4.463104e-02 0.003163065 -0.14503067 0.7397260
1100  IS17 0.009575978 1.142529e-02 0.011204547 -0.05872777 0.5205479
1101  IS18 0.097071054 6.438580e-02 0.058855505 -0.25304859 0.9452055
1102  IS19 0.050612976 8.190827e-02 0.075259785 -0.17785521 0.5217391
1103
1104  $overall
1105  NorthSouth Area Site Ind Error
1106  0.5167495 0.3569386 0.2377869 -0.6790641 6.4613395
1107
1108  $F
1109      NorthSouth Area Site Ind
1110  Total 0.07495912 0.12673626 0.16122936 0.06272506
1111  NorthSouth 0.00000000 0.05597281 0.09326101 -0.01322543
1112  Area 0.00000000 0.00000000 0.03949907 -0.07330110
1113  Site 0.00000000 0.00000000 0.00000000 -0.11743890

```

```
1114
1115 > test.within(loci,test=Site,within=Area,nperm=1000)
1116 $p.val
1117 [1] 0.023
1118
1119 > test.between.within(loci,within=NorthSouth,rand.unit=Site,test=Area,nperm=1000)
1120 $p.val
1121 [1] 0.037
1122
1123 > test.between(loci,rand.unit=Area,test=NorthSouth,nperm=1000)
1124 $p.val
1125 [1] 0.186
```

```
1126
1127 Appendix 2: Scripts for the geosphere analysis (geographic distance and surface
1128 computations)
```

```
1129
1130 Computing geographic distances between subsample pairs defined by Site-Cohort
1131 combinations
```

```
1132 The first file containing the GPS coordinates in decimal degree (longitude and
1133 latitude) of the first site of each site pair was "LongLat1.txt", and the second one
1134 "LongLat2.txt".
```

```
1135 LongLat1 <- read.table("LongLat1.txt", header=TRUE)
1136 LongLat2 <- read.table("LongLat2.txt", header=TRUE)
1137 tabDistGeo<-data.frame(distGeo(LongLat1,LongLat2))
1138 write.table(tabDistGeo,"TabDistGeo.txt",col=NA, sep="\t", dec=".")
```

```
1139
1140 Computing surfaces of a sub-population or of the entire land covered by samples of
1141 genotyped adult ticks
```

```
1142
1143 Dataset <- read.table("LongLatWI.txt", header=TRUE)
1144 attach(Dataset)
1145 areaPolygon(data.frame(Longitude, Latitude))
1146 [1] 13062561
1147
1148 Dataset <- read.table("I-scap-LongLat4Corners.txt", header=TRUE)
1149 attach(Dataset)
1150 areaPolygon(data.frame(Longitude, Latitude))
1151 [1] 129132161155
```